

Binomial Coefficients and Factorials for Non-Negative Real Numbers

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Abstract: This paper presents a technique to calculate the factorials for non-negative real numbers. This is also applicable for the coefficients of geometric series.

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1. Introduction

In general, the factorial for non-negative integer n , denoted by $n!$, is the product of all positive integers less than or equal to n . Similar, we can find the factorial for non-negative real number in the article.

A geometric series with binomial coefficients [1-17] is derived from the multiple summations of a geometric series [17-27]. The binomial coefficient V_n^r is defined as a coefficient of x^k in the geometric series $\sum_{i=0}^n x^i$.

Let us see the geometric series with binomial coefficients that is derived from the multiple summations of a geometric series [28-40].

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \dots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \text{ and } V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\dots(n+r)}{r!},$$

where r is a positive integer and n is a non-negative integer.

$$\text{Note that } V_n^0 = V_0^0 = 0! = 1 \text{ and } V_0^r = \frac{(0+1)(0+2)(0+3)\dots(0+r)}{r!} = \frac{r!}{r!} = 1.$$

2. Factorials for Real numbers

Let $x = i.f$ be a real number, where i is an integer part and f is the decimal or fractional part and $x \geq 1$.

$$x! = (i.f)! = i! + \{(i+1)! - i!\} \times (0.f).$$

OR

$$x! = (i.f)! = (i+1)! - (1-0.f)\{(i+1)! - i!\}.$$

$$\text{For example, } (4.6)! = 4! + 0.6(5! - 4!) = 24 + 0.6(120 - 24) = 81.6.$$

(OR)

$$(4.6)! = 5! - (1 - 0.6)(5! - 4!) = 120 - 0.4(120 - 24) = 81.6.$$

3. Binomial Coefficient with Real Numbers

Let us use both variables in a binomial coefficient V_x^y as non-negative real numbers, i.e. x and y are non-negative real numbers and $y \geq 1$.

$$V_x^y = V_x^{i.f} = V_x^i + (V_x^{i+1} - V_x^i) \times (0.f), \text{ where } y \geq 1.$$

For example, $y = i.f = 3.7 = 3 + 0.7$ where 3 is the integer part and 0.7 the fractional part,

$$i. e., \quad V_x^{3.7} = V_x^3 + (0.7)(V_x^4 - V_x^3).$$

(OR)

$$V_x^y = V_x^{i.f} = V_x^{i+1} - (1 - 0.f)(V_x^{i+1} - V_x^i), \text{ where } y \geq 1.$$

For example, $y = i.f = 3.7 = 3 + 0.7$ where 3 is the integer part and 0.7 the fraction part,

$$i. e., \quad V_x^{3.7} = V_x^4 - (0.3)(V_x^4 - V_x^3).$$

4. Conclusion

In this article, a technique has been introduced to compute the binomial coefficients and factorials for non-negative real numbers. This technique is used as application in computing and mathematical sciences.

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